

Donor Behaviour of Isoperthiocyanic Acid and Cyanoimidodithiocarbonic Acid with some Metal Ions

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An interesting route for the preparation of the complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Cu^I with cyanoimidodithiocarbonic acid (LH₂) and isoperthiocyanic acid (L'H₂) is reported. The complexes of composition [MLPy₂] (M = Co, Ni, Zn or Cd), [Cu₂LPy₂], [NiLPy₃.H₂O], [ML'(H₂O)₂] (M = Zn, Cd, Ni) have been prepared.

The formation of cyanoimidodithiocarbonic acid (LH₂) and isoperthiocyanic acid (L'H₂) have been reported in solution¹. The present paper reports the isolation of their compounds in fairly stable form as their metal complexes.

Results and Discussion

3-Amino-5-thione-1,2,4-dithiazole (AMT) has been reported to undergo structural rearrangement in alkaline medium into isoperthiocyanic acid (L'H₂) through an intermediate product cyanoimidodithiocarbonic acid (LH₂)¹ (Scheme 1).

From the analytical and physical data (Table 1) it has been concluded that complexes of AMT is not formed. In

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES*

Compd.	Colour	Metal % : Found/(Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.
[CoLPy ₂]	Brown	17.27 (17.72)	3.96
[NiLPy ₂]	Yellow	16.93 (17.72)	2.87
[NiLPy ₃ .H ₂ O]	Green	12.96 (13.72)	3.21
[Cu ₂ LPy ₂]	Brown	30.98 (31.67)	Dia
ZnLPy ₂	Yellow	18.72 (19.17)	Dia
[CoLPy ₂]	Yellow	28.13 (29.01)	Dia
[NiL'(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	24.26 (24.09)	3.07
[ZnL'(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	29.60 (30.25)	Dia
[CdL']	Yellow	41.87 (42.75)	Dia

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

weakly alkaline medium (in pyridine solution) the ligand is transformed to cyanoimidodithiocarbonic acid (LH₂) and its solid insoluble complexes of compositions MLPy₂ (M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}) and NiLPy₃.H₂O are formed. In strongly alkaline medium (~2 N NaOH) the ligand is transformed to isoperthiocyanic acid (L'H₂) and its complexes of composition [ML'.nH₂O] (M = Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}; n = 2 or 0) have been isolated. In case of copper, the ligand reduces Cu^{II} to Cu^I and Cu^I complex of (LH₂) of composition [Cu₂LPy₂] is formed. To ascertain the formation, the Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were prepared independently from authentic solution of H₂L and H₂L'. The analytical and physical data of the complexes were found to be similar from both the procedures.

In general, the complexes are insoluble in water and ethanol but sparingly soluble in DMF, indicating their polymeric nature. The dried complexes do not lose water or pyridine below 100° indicating them to be coordinated.

The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic. Copper complex [Cu₂LPy₂] is also diamagnetic supporting oxidation state +1 for copper. The Ni^{II} complexes [NiLPy₂], [NiLPy₃.H₂O] and [NiL'(H₂O)₂] display magnetic moment value in the range 2.87–3.21 B.M., similar to spin-free octahedral or pseudo-tetrahedral complexes³. Magnetic moment value of [CoLPy₂] found to be 3.96 B.M. at room temperature, is lower than for spin-free octahedral Co^{II} complexes². Hence, four-coordinated tetrahedral geometry is indicated for Co^{II}.

Due to insolubility, electronic absorption spectra of the complexes could not be recorded in solution. The solid reflectance spectrum of [CoLPy₂] displays broad and strong absorption at 30 000–20 000 cm⁻¹ attributable to charge transfer band. The complex shows a triplet at 18 500–14 500 cm⁻¹ and a broad band at 9 090–7 700 cm⁻¹ assignable to ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₁ (P) and ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₁ (F) transitions in tetrahedral field^{2,3}. The reflectance spectrum of [Cu₂LPy₂] displays a broad band near 23 810 cm⁻¹ attributable to charge transfer band. [NiLPy₂] shows a broad absorption between 30 000 and 20 000 cm⁻¹ due to C-T ab-

sorption. The broad and strong absorptions at 17 240, 9 090 and 6 060 cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3T_1$ (P), ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3T_2$ and $\rightarrow {}^3A_2$ transitions respectively in pseudo-tetrahedral field⁴. The reflectance bands of $[\text{NiLPy}_3\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ show a broad C-T band at 29 400 cm^{-1} and *d-d* bands at 23 530, 17 240 and 9 710 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ transitions in approximately octahedral field⁴. The reflectance spectrum of $[\text{NiL}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ shows *d-d* transitions at 23 810, 16 660, 11 900 and 8 750 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}$, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_{2g}$ transitions respectively, in distorted octahedral field⁴. The reflectance bands of the complexes are not well-resolved, indicating a large tetragonal distortions. Thus calculations of ligand field parameters were considered futile.

The ir spectrum of the starting material AMT displays ν_{NH_2} as strong band at 3 200 and δ_{NH_2} at 1 500 cm^{-1} . These bands disappeared in isoperthiocyanic acid complexes $[\text{ML}'\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ($M = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}) formed in strongly alkaline medium, indicating the absence of NH_2 group and conversion of AMT to $\text{L}'\text{H}_2$. The $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ band of AMT observed at 1 620 cm^{-1} , is also present in the transformed compound (1 600–1 620 cm^{-1}). The strong $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ band (1 325 cm^{-1}) of AMT was absent in the complexes, indicating the absence of C=S group in the complexes which further supported the transformation of AMT to $\text{L}'\text{H}_2$. The bands at 1 080 and 1 000 cm^{-1} were assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ vibrations. The transformed product also possesses C-N bond and the $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ bands in complexes were observed at 1 080–1 040 and 1 000–922 cm^{-1} . The complexes displayed a new band at 720–690 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ of coordinated $\text{L}'\text{H}_2$. The aquo complexes $[\text{ML}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ displayed a broad band near 3 300 cm^{-1} $\nu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$. The $\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ band of water molecule in the complexes merged with $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ near 1 600 cm^{-1} . The broad and weak band near 660 ± 5 cm^{-1} were attributed to ρ_w band of coordinated water molecule⁵. The ir spectra of the complexes prepared from authentic solution of $\text{L}'\text{H}_2$ were superimposable to compounds formed from transformed product of AMT.

The ir spectra of the complexes $[\text{MLPy}_2]$ ($M = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, Co^{II} , Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}) and $[\text{NiLPy}_3\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ formed in pyridine solution from cyanoimidodithiocarbonyl acid (LH_2) displayed the absence of ν_{NH_2} , δ_{NH_2} and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ vibrations of AMT. Besides, the absence of characteristic AMT bands, the complexes showed the appearance of a new and strong band at 2 095–2 000 cm^{-1} which decidedly supports the formation of (C≡N) group due to conversion of AMT to LH_2 during complexation in pyridine medium⁵. The spectrum of $[\text{NiLPy}_3\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ showed $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ as strong band at 2 095 cm^{-1} , whereas $[\text{MLPy}_2]$ ($M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ or Ni^{II}) showed $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ band at 2 200–2 180 cm^{-1} . The occurrence of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ at higher frequency in $[\text{MLPy}_2]$ ($M = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ or Co^{II}) suggested that C≡N nitrogen is free in these complexes, while it is attached to pyridine in $[\text{NiLPy}_3\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ or involved in hydrogen bonding with H_2O . The presence of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ band at 2 090–1 110 cm^{-1} in $[\text{Cu}_2\text{LPy}_2]$ and $[\text{MLPy}_2]$ ($M = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ or

Cd^{II}) suggested the involvement of C≡N nitrogen in bonding. The new band observed at 690–710 cm^{-1} in the complexes is attributed to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ stretch which is generated on transformation of AMT and thereafter bonded to metal ion on deprotonation. The pyridine complexes showed new bands at 1 596 ± 4 , 1 210 ± 2 , 1 065 ± 2 , 1 005 ± 5 , 755 ± 5 , 695 ± 5 and 625 ± 5 cm^{-1} . These bands are characteristic vibrations of coordinated pyridine^{5,6}.

In far-infrared region, the complexes display two or three medium bands at 500–250 cm^{-1} , which have been tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{S}}$ vibrations⁷.

The ir spectral studies also support the complex formation from intermediate compound as well as transformation product of AMT in alkaline medium. In complexes, L^{2-} acts as bidentate molecule forming bonds through both of deprotonated dithiocarbonyl sulphur. In case of complexes $[\text{ML}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]$, the isoperthiocyanate anion appears to be bonded as dianionic bridging quadridentate molecule forming bond through both N and S atoms.

Experimental

H_2L and $\text{H}_2\text{L}'$ were obtained in solution by dissolving solid 3-amino-5-thione-1,2,4-dithiazole by the reported method¹.

$[\text{MLPy}_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}_2\text{LPy}_2]$ ($M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$, Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} or Cd^{II} , $L = \text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}_2^{2-}$): A solution of metal acetate (~0.01 mol) dissolved in aqueous methanol (50 ml) and pyridine (5 ml) was treated with stoichiometric ratio of AMT (0.012 mol) dissolved in methanol-pyridine mixture. The dipyrindino complexes that separated immediately, was centrifuged, washed with methanol containing a few drops of pyridine and dried in a desiccator over KOH. The dried sample was suspended in CS_2 containing a few drops of pyridine, filtered and dried as above.

$[\text{NiLPy}_3\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ($L = \text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}_2^{2-}$): Nickel chloride (~0.01 mol) dissolved in aqueous methanol (30 ml) and pyridine (5 ml), was mixed with alkaline solution of AMT (0.012 mol) in 2 N aqueous sodium acetate (30–40 ml) and pyridine (5 ml) with stirring. The resulting greenish blue solid was centrifuged, washed and dried as above.

$[\text{ML}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ ($L' = \text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}_3^{2-}$; $M = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}): AMT (~0.02 mol) dissolved in 2 N NaOH (30–40 ml) was treated with aqueous ammoniacal solution of stoichiometric proportion of metal chloride with stirring when the complexes separated immediately. The product was washed with water and ethanol and dried in air oven at 70–80°.

Diffused reflectance spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 700 spectrophotometer at I.I.T., Delhi and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer at Patna University. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy method⁸ at room temperature (304 K).

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